

Development of an *in situ* consolidated nanocrystalline Cu₈₈Al_{11.5}Y_{0.5} alloy

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Nanocrystalline Cu₈₈Al_{11.5}Y_{0.5} bulk alloy has been synthesized by *in situ* consolidation of mechanically alloyed powder blend followed by annealing of the consolidated compact at 200° C (or 0.35 T_m) for 30 min. Grain size determination and phase identification have been carried by X-ray line broadening analysis and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Hardness measurement has demonstrated that the Hall-Petch effect is the dominant strengthening mechanism for both as-consolidated and annealed specimens. Strength improvement after short annealing time was attributed to the relaxations of non-equilibrium grain boundaries.

Keywords: Nanocrystalline copper alloys, Mechanical alloying, *In situ* consolidation, strengthening mechanism

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